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Impact Factor: 3.43

DOES MICRO FINANCE A SOLUTION FOR POVERTY ERADICATION? A STUDY OF DISTRICT RAJOURI

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ABSTRACT

Micro credit Programs extend small loans to very poor people for self employment projects that generate income for their survival, allowing them to care for themselves and their families. Microfinance is seen as a key development tool and is now being considered as one of the most important and an effective means for poverty alleviation microfinance schemes are also considered as an effective mechanisms through which the disseminate of precious information on ways to improve the health, education, legal rights, sanitation and other living standards, which are of relevant concerns for the poor. Microfinance has been heralded as the solution to global poverty by optimists in the development field. Many regard the practice of extending unprecedented financial access to the poor through small loans as a necessary and important tool in the development process. The industry has grown and changed shape over the last two decades and recently has come under fire.

Key Words: *Microfinance, poverty, financial access, poverty, legal rights and small loans.*

INTRODUCTION

Microfinance has eradicated the poverty of many people by giving small loans to small family. Micro finance includes small loans to foster small scale entrepreneurial activities so that livelihood of people can be enhanced .such credit would otherwise not be available if available at very high costs i.e. 10 to 13% depending upon the institutions which are providing loans.

Moneylenders operate with little competition since potential entrants quickly find that costs and risks are high and borrowers are usually unable to offer standard forms of collateral, if any at all. However, the emerging microfinance movement demonstrates institutional innovations that appear to greatly reduce the risk and cost of providing financial services to poor households. Innovations include contracts that give borrowers incentives to exclude bad credit risks and monitor other borrowers' activities, schedules of loans that increase over time

conditional on successful performance, and weekly or semi-weekly loan repayment requirement. The movement is now global, and leaders at the World Bank, United Nations, and other international organizations have joined in pushing to reach 100 million households around the world. But how great is the ultimate impact on poor households? While strong claims are made for the ability of microfinance to reduce poverty, only a handful of studies use sizeable samples and appropriate treatment/control frameworks to answer the question. The three lending programs considered here together serve over four million poor clients in Bangladesh, but their role is much broader. The Grameen Bank is the flagship of the international microfinance movement, and its model has now been replicated on four continents, including sites in the United States as varied as rural Arkansas and inner-city Chicago. Simple estimates of impacts show clear achievements. For example, if household's served by the Grameen Bank are ordered by the amounts they have borrowed from the program, the top quarter enjoys 15% higher consumption per capita than households in the bottom quarter. In addition, 62% of the school-age sons of Grameen Bank borrowers are enrolled in school versus 34% of the sons of eligible households that do not borrow. For daughters, the Grameen advantage is 55% versus 40%. These simple comparisons appear to be driven entirely by selection biases, however. Once appropriate comparisons with control groups are made, access to the three microfinance programs does not yield meaningful increases in per capita consumption, the education of sons, nor the education of daughters. If anything, the levels are slightly lower than for control groups. The results are surprising and contradict frequent claims made about the programs in international discussions of microfinance.

Access to the programs does; however, appear to aid the diversification of labour supply across seasons. In turn, access is associated with a reduction in the variability of consumption across seasons. Thus, while the programs may not increase consumption on average, they may offer households ways to smooth consumption through smoothing income. In pointing to impacts on vulnerability, the results highlight an advantage that is seldom considered in the emerging microfinance literature). These benefits should be judged against the tens of millions of dollars that have supported the programs. The results also demonstrate how misleading simple performance indicators can be, and they hold lessons for evaluations of similar public health and other social programs in low-income countries. As here, such programs are often limited to particular regions and particular target groups, typically poor households. Unlike in wealthier countries, income-based means tests are almost never used. Instead, for example, the microfinance programs in rural Bangladesh focus on the

“functionally landless” -- implemented as a rule barring lending to households owning over a half acre of cultivable land. The program rule can be the basis of a plausible econometric strategy if the eligibility requirement is strictly enforced and built around a feature that is exogenous to the household. Then, clean impacts can be gauged by comparing the status of households clustered just below the arbitrary dividing line to households clustered just above.

Review of literature

Abiola & Salami (2011), in his study mentioned that a lot of literature is present on the positive role of micro finance in poverty alleviation, but every time and everywhere, microfinance is not so profitable. Many scholars wrote that micro finance is a good tool for poverty alleviation but in many occasion the result is opposite. The main reason behind the negative effect of the micro finance on poverty alleviation is due to the time shortage. The time is not enough for generating the income i.e. the shortness do not give room for loan to generate future income. Sita Devi.K, Ponnarasi.T & Tamil Selvi.G (2010), in this research paper aims to analyze the impact of microfinance on the socio-economic status of the rural poor in Cuddalore District of Tamil Nadu. Hassan (2010), Mentioned the reasons behind success of micro finance and highlights no collateral against loans. The negative point of the conventional micro finance is the fixed high interest rate. Interest is not acceptable in Islam that is why the Muslim clients prefer Islamic micro finance. According to the researcher, if conventional micro finance is combined with the Islamic financial system like Zakat and Awqaf, the result will be different. Imai, Gaiha, Thapa and Annim (2010), concluded that there is no doubt micro finance is a powerful tool against poverty but some evidence creates a black spot on its performance. The study proved that the number of poor people’s is less in those countries where the number of micro finance institutions is more in compare to those countries where the number of MFIs are less. David Roodman 2009, called 2009 a “milestone year for microfinance” and it certainly, providing two separate randomized studies on the impact of microcredit. Simultaneously, other studies have also emerged on the broader topic of microfinance. Yet, certainly the literature of microfinance cannot be so new. After all, governments have long known that increasing access to rural and low-income finance was important. India instituted a rural bank expansion program in 1977. Mexico did something similar in 1992. Gurses (2009), conducted a study in Turkey and mentioned that micro finance especially micro credit is a powerful tool to reduce poverty. Shastri (2009), revealed that there no way better then microfinance in the war against poverty. Creating self employment

opportunities is one way of attacking poverty and solving the problems of unemployment. The authors reported that there are over 24 crore people below the poverty line in India. The Scheme of Micro-finance has been found as an effective instrument for lifting the poor above the level of poverty by providing them self-employment opportunities and making them credit worthy. Shirazi and Khan (2009), show that two types of poor were taken in consideration such as the poor and the extreme poor. The authors examined the impact of micro credit on poverty alleviation. Micro credit had reduced the overall poverty level by 3.07 percentage points (from 6.61 percent to 3.54 percent) and the borrowers have shifted to higher income groups during the reported period. The poverty status of the extremely poor borrowers has been marginally increased (by 0.63 percentage point), showing obviously no effect of micro credit on poverty status of these households. The reason behind no effect of micro credit on extremely poor is that, the extreme poor get the loan for protective purposes not for further income or self employment. In case of ultra poor, the net impact of micro credit shows a reduction by 1.45 percentages a point which is a positive impact.

Objective of the study

- 1: To know about the socio economic status of beneficiaries in the study area
- 2: To study the impact of microfinance programmes on poverty alleviation

Research methodology

Sources of Data: The study is undertaken in rural areas of district Rajouri of Jammu and Kashmir. Both primary and secondary data's are used. Primary data is enumerated from a field survey in the study region. Secondary data is collected from NGOs' reports and other documents. Areas covered under the study are two tehsils namely Koteranka and Darhal and villages selected from these two tehsils are as under:

- 1: Koteranka
 - a) Kurhad
 - b) Peeri
 - c) Panihad
- 2: Darhal
 - a) Dodaj
 - b) Nadian Rakiban

SELECTION OF THE STUDY AREA AND SAMPLE DESIGN

District Rajouri is selected for the present study, Rajouri is located in the foothills of Peer-Panjal range of Himalayas, with an area of 2,630 sq.km in the west of Jammu division In district Rajouri there are seven tehsils namely; Rajouri, Nowshera, Sunderbani, Kalakote, Koteranka (Budhal), Thannamandi and Darhal out of these Tehsils only two Tehsils were taken for the present study and from these two Tehsils namely koteranka and Darhal, only five villages were selected for the present study. The respondents shall be selected on the basics of area sampling and stratified random sampling technique.

Sample Size: 100 samples have been collected for the research from two tehsils of district Rajouri namely Koteranka and Darhal and out of two tehsils five villages i.e. three villages from koteranka Tehsil and two villages from Darhal Tehsil have been selected for the study from district Rajouri.

Statistical tools used: percentage analysis, cross tabulation and Chi-square has been used to analyze and interpret the data.

Method of Data Collection: A structured interview schedule was prepared by the researcher and used for collecting data from the beneficiaries who are engaged in Micro enterprises through microfinance.

Limitations of the Study

- 1: A minimum sample should have been taken from MFP providers and receivers, other stakeholders should also be involved in the study.
- 2: Many of the respondents couldn't cooperate, because of their busy schedule and data confidentiality policies of the organizations.
- 3: The study is confined with the beneficiaries of microfinance in some areas of district Rajouri. Hence the results may not be applicable to whole district and whole beneficiaries of microfinance and the data was collected only from those who engaged in income generating activities.

Data analysis and interpretation

The analysis of data has been carried out by using simple percentage analysis, cross tabulation, chi-square test. The outcome of data analysis is given in next sections.

Table No. 1.1 Gender wise distribution of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	70	70
Female	30	30
Total	100	100.0

Table shows the gender wise distribution of respondents and shows that 70% respondents were male and 30% were female

Table No. 1.2 Age-wise distribution of the respondents

Age	Frequency	Percent
18-25	14	14
26-30	21	21
31-35	17	17
36-40	25	25
41 and Above	23	23
Total	100	100.0

Age wise distribution of the respondents shows that age group of 36-40 have 25% respondent followed by age group from 41 and above that is 23%, 26-30 have 21% , 31-35 have 17% and 18-25 only 14% respondents

Table No. 1.3 Income of the respondents

Income	Frequency	Percent
0-5k	05	5
6-10k	12	12
11-15K	20	20
16-20K	23	23
21-25K	19	19
26K and Above	21	21
Total	100	100.0

Income wise distribution of the respondents shows that income group of 16-20k have maximum respondents 23% followed by income group from 26k and above have 21%

Table1.4 Education wise distribution of the respondents

Education	Frequency	Percent
Up to 8 th	14	14
10 th	23	23
Higher sec.	43	43
Grad. And above	20	20
Total	100	100

Education of beneficiaries is concerned out of 100 respondents 43 (43%) are from higher secondary followed by high standard (10th) 23 (23%) respondents, graduation and above 20 (20%) and up to middle 14 (14%) respondents.

Table 1.5: shows associations between impact of microfinance programmes on poverty alleviation and Income of the entrepreneurs

Chi-Square Tests	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	127.293a	10	.000
Likelihood Ratio	134.901	10	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	78.945	1	.000

a. 2 cells (11.1%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.14.

Associations between impact of microfinance programmes on poverty alleviation and Income of the entrepreneurs have been studied. In order to test the association chi square test have been applied table 1.5. It has been found that the chi-square test of association value is 127.293 with degrees of freedom at 10 and the 'p' value is 0.000. As the 'p' value is less than 0.05, it indicates that the impact of microfinance programmes on poverty alleviation is significantly influenced by the Income of entrepreneurs.

Table1.6: study the associations between impact of microfinance programmes on poverty alleviation and age of the respondents

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	158.926a	8	.000
Likelihood Ratio	190.921	8	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	18.692	1	.000

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 12.16.

Associations between impact of microfinance programmes on poverty alleviation and age of the entrepreneurs have been studied. In order to test the association, chi square test of association have been applied table 1.6. It has been found that the chi-square test of association value is 158.926 with degrees of freedom at 8 and the ‘p’ value is 0.000. As the ‘p’ value is less than 0.05, it indicates that the impact of socio economic factors on poverty alleviation is significantly influenced by the age of entrepreneurs.

Table1.7: shows the associations between impact of microfinance programmes on poverty alleviation and gender of the entrepreneurs.

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.818a	2	.403
Likelihood Ratio	1.840	2	.398
Linear-by-Linear Association	.577	1	.448

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 26.39.

Associations between impact of microfinance programmes on poverty alleviation and gender of the entrepreneurs have been studied. In order to test the association, chi square have been applied table 1.7. It has been found that the chi-square test of association value is 1.818 with degrees of freedom at 2 and the ‘p’ value is 0.403. As the ‘p’ value is greater than 0.05, it indicates that the impact of microfinance programmes on poverty alleviation is not significantly influenced by the gender of entrepreneurs.

Table1.8: shows the associations between impact of microfinance programmes on poverty alleviation and education of the entrepreneurs.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	117.471 ^a	6	.000
Likelihood Ratio	136.981	6	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.271	1	.603

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 12.42.

Associations between impact of microfinance programmes on poverty alleviation and education of the entrepreneurs have been studied. In order to test the association, chi-square has been applied table 1.8. It has been found that the chi-square test of association value is 117.471 with degrees of freedom at 6 and the 'p' value is 0.000. As the 'p' value is less than 0.05, it indicates that the Poverty is significantly influenced by the education of entrepreneurs.

Findings of the study:

1. It revealed that out of 100 respondents selected for the study, 70 (70%) were males and 30 (30%) were females.
2. Majority of them belonged to the age group of 36-40 years and minimum in the age group of 18-25.
3. Most of them were in the income group of Rs. 16000-20000.
4. As for as education of the beneficiaries is concerned out of 100 respondents 43 (43%) are from higher secondary followed by high standard (10th) 23 (23%) respondents, graduation and above 20 (20%) and up to middle 14 (14%) respondents.
5. It has been found that impacts of socio economic factors on poverty alleviation are significantly influenced.
6. It has been found that impact of microfinance programmes on poverty alleviation are significantly influenced by the different variables such as Income, gender, age and education of the entrepreneurs/respondents.
7. It is also found that the accounts of the respondents are not managed properly by the microfinance providers.

8. It has been found that there is increase in the income of the respondents after the utilization of financial assistance from MFPs.
9. It has been found that there is improvement in the socio economic status of the respondents after using microfinance schemes.
10. It has also been found that the MFP alleviates the poverty level of the poor and respondents and as it shows a positive trend.

Suggestions & Recommendations

The following few suggestions and recommendations have being made which include;

- I. Creation of awareness among SHGs: The Government must start some awareness among the SHGs so that they can understand different schemes in a better way.
- II. Organization of credit camps Credit camps should be organized at block level and Gram panchayat level with block representatives, bank officials, experts from various development departments of government and professional organizations.
- III. Block and bank officials should make surprise and frequent visit to the respondents to ensure the proper utilization of bank loan on various economic activities.
- IV. Managing the accounts in a proper way: the accounts of the beneficiaries in a proper way.
- V. Training programme for up gradations of skills: it is found that there is no such training programmes for the respondent .these programmes must be started so that the respondent utilised their skills in the a proper and in suitable way
- VI. Proper follow up and effective supervision
- VII. Ensuring NGOs participation in encouraging the beneficiaries

To sum up it may be concluded that microfinance schemes which should otherwise have brought about a formidable change on the socio-economic front in the far flung areas of the country has not gone well for lack of effective implementation and ethical approaches to carry out the implementation of these programmes. In fact it has been the tragedy of our system that the microfinance schemes which have been well conceived of & aimed to bring about qualitative changes in the life of rural masses but unfortunately poor implementation and then inappropriate utilisation of the microfinance schemes failed to yield the desired results.

References

- Bansal,A.K.(2012).Microfinance And Poverty Reduction In India. *A Journal of Management*, 5(1), 31-35.
- Chavan, P.(2002). Micro-credit and Rural Poverty: An Analysis of empirical evidence. *Economic and Political weekly*, 37(10), 955-965.
- Chibba, M. (2007). Monetary Policy, Governance and Economic Development: The Botswana experience. *World Economics*, 8(3), 111–129.
- Copestake, J. (2001). Assessing the impact of microcredit: A Zambian case study. *Journal of Development Studies*,4(37),81-100.
- Dasgupta, R. (2001). Working and Impact of Rural Self-Help Groups and other Forms of Micro Financing: An Informal Journey Through Self-Help Groups. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 56(3), 370-386.
- Davis, Y. (1999). The multi-layered citizen, Citizenship in the age of ‘globalization. *International Feminist Journal of Politics*, 1 (1), 119-136.
- Diane, C. (2007). How to Tackle Poverty: Economists are closing in on the answers. *World Economics*, 8(3), 1–5.
- Evans, P. (1996). Government Action, Social Capital and Development: Reviewing the Evidence on Synergy, *World Development*, 24(6),119 132,
- Hamdani,S.Q.M.(2012). The Impact Of Microfinance On Social Mobility, An Empirical Evidence From Pakistan. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research In Business*, 3(9), 81-88.
- Hamed. (2011).Impact of Microfinance on Poverty Alleviation in Nigeria: *An Empirical Investigation & European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*,2(1), 97-111.
- Hulme,D.(2000).Impact Assessment Methodologies for Microfinance: Theory, Experience and Better Practice, *World Development*,28(1), 79-98.
- Hussain, I. (2011). The Role of Microfinance in uplifting Income Level: A study of District Okara - Pakistan. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research In Business*, 2(11), 83-89.
- Islam, N & Mamun, M. Z. (2005). Factors for Not Buying Life Insurance Policies in a Developing Country: A Case of Bangladesh. *Journal of Business Administration, Institute of Business Administration, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh*, 31(2), 1-22